

Challenges Facing the Administration of Higher Institutions in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract:

The study investigated the challenges facing the administration of higher institutions in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The descriptive survey design was used and the study was guided by six hypotheses. The population of the study comprised of [90] schools administrators (Head of department of academic and Non-academic units and department) in three sampled public higher institutions in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. Purposive sampling method was used to select the sample for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire which was developed by the researcher and the questionnaire was titled the 'Challenges Facing Administration of Higher institutions Questionnaire' (CFAHIQ). The questionnaire was validated by two experts in Educational Management in University of Abuja. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using the test-retest method and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis which yielded a co-efficient of 0.78. Data collected by the questionnaire were analyzed using simple percentage and Chi-square. Result collected and analyzed in this study established that inadequate fund, inadequate infrastructural facilities, shortage of staff, high student enrollment is strike action is a challenge facing the administration of higher institutions in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria and political influence are the challenge facing the administration of higher institutions in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

Keyword: Challenges, Administration, Higher institutions